

Spectrophotometric Studies on Fe(III) with *p*-Dimethylaminoanil of 2,5 - Dihydroxyacetophenone

P. SINGH*, V. SINGH, B. P. SINGH, G. P. POKHARYAL and R. P. MAHESH

Chemical Laboratories, S. S. V. College, Hapur (Meerut)

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Fe(III) forms a pinkish red complex with Paradimethyl-aminoanil of 2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone. The complex exhibits maximum absorption at 440 nm. The composition of the complex (1 : 2) has been determined by Job's method of continuous variation, mole ratio method and slope ratio method employing spectrophotometric data. The dissociation constant is 16.99×10^{10} at 30° and the standard free energy formation of the complex is -15.44 K. Cal/mole. The composition of the complex is further confirmed by elemental analysis and spectral studies.

P-DIMETHYL aminoanil of 2,5-dihydroxy acetophenone (PDAAP) behaves as a good chelating agent¹⁻³ for a number of transition metal ions. The present work deals with the spectrophotometric study of the complex formation of Fe(III) with PDAAP, using spectrophotometric methods.⁴⁻⁷

Experimental

Ferric chloride and the other chemicals used were of A.R. quality.

A spectronic '20' spectrophotometer was used for the measurement.

A Guoy balance is used for magnetic measurement.

I.R. Spectra were carried out on Perkin Elmer Infracord Spectrophotometer model-521 in KBr pellets.

Spectrophotometric study

The equimolar solutions of ferric chloride and the ligand in the ratio of 2 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, and 1 : 3 were mixed and final volume was made 20 ml by adding required amount of water and alcohol to keep alcohol water composition the same in all cases. The absorption spectra of all solutions were taken. In all cases the maximum absorption was found to be at 440 nm suggesting the formation of only one type of complex with the ligand.

Composition of the complex

Job's method of continuous variations, molar ratio method and slope ratio method were employed to determine the stoichiometry (metal : ligand) of the complex. The results of these methods showed 1 : 2 composition. Vosburgh and Cooper's method indicated 440 nm as the optimum wavelength for spectrophotometric studies. To avoid the personal error

of experimentation, it has been customary⁸ to make studies $\pm(10-20)$ nm to the suitable wavelength. The measurements of optical density were made at 460 nm and 440 nm, however similar results were obtained at 430 nm.

The dissociation constant of the complex was calculated by the molar ratio method. The value of K as calculated came out to be 16.99×10^{10} . The standard free energy of complex formation, ΔF° , was calculated from the relation $\Delta F^\circ = -RT \log K$ and is found to be -15.44 K.cal/mole.

Isolation

The stoichiometric mixture of metal salt and the ligand in alcoholic medium was refluxed on water bath for half an hour and cooled. A pinkish red coloured complex deposited which was washed with water and ethanol and dried. The solid complex was purified by crystallisation from ethanol. The complex does not decompose upto 350°. Chemical analysis results confirm the proposed composition 1 : 2. The complex compound in DMF exhibits molar conductance $115 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ indicating a univalent character. The presence of one hydrogen ion in the complex is confirmed by the fact that one g. equivalent of caustic soda is required for its complete neutralisation. Found : C, 57.50; H, 5.10; N, 8.20; Cl, 10.34; Fe, 8.34. Calcd : for Fe, C₃₂H₃₅O₄N₄Cl₂. C, 57.65; H, 5.93; N, 8.41; Cl, 10.67; Fe, 8.41.

Magnetic and spectral studies

The value of magnetic moment 5.80 B.M. suggests either formation of octahedral or a polymeric complex.¹¹ But the details of element analysis only favour the octahedral stereochemistry. In the electronic spectra of Fe(III) complex in DMF and acetone four bands are obtained (Fig. 1).

* For correspondence.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of $H[Fe(C_{32}H_{34}N_4O_4)Cl_2]$. Wavelength in cm^{-1} .

[A] $0.08 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution in DMF.

[B] $0.07 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution in Acetone.

Observed bands	Splitting energy cm^{-1}	Racah Parameter B cm^{-1}
20,000 cm^{-1}		
23,265 cm^{-1}	9163	833
26,350 cm^{-1}		
28,400 cm^{-1}		

These bands may be assigned the transitions^{9,10} ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(G)$ and the fourth band at higher energy may be considered as a charge transfer band. This favours an octahedral symmetry for the complex.¹⁰

As compared to the ligand in the i.r. spectrum of the complex, the stretching frequencies of azomethine

($CH_3C=N$) and hydroxyl (OH) groups are lowered and bands around 1490 cm^{-1} and 3270 cm^{-1} appear respectively, showing thereby complex formation through these groups. This view is further supported by the appearance of bands corresponding to M-N (495 cm^{-1}) and M-O (460 cm^{-1}) bonds. Metal to halogen bond formed is indicated by the lowering of stretching frequency due to chlorine. The band at 3280 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of other unreacted hydroxyl group of the ligand. Tentative structure of the complex is given column 1.

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References

1. P. SINGH and V. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 734.
2. P. SINGH and V. SINGH, *Current Sci.* (In press)
3. P. SINGH and V. SINGH, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, (In press)
4. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim. (Paris)*; 1928, 9, 13.
5. W. C. VOSBURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437.
6. J. H. YOY and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.
7. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*; 1950, 72, 4448.
8. W. U. MALIK and R. C. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 699.
9. C. J. BALLHAUSEN, 'Introduction to Ligand Field Theory'. Mc-Graw Hill Book Co. N.Y. 1962.
10. B. N. FIGGIS, 'Introduction to Ligand Fields'. John Wiley and Sons Inc. N.Y. 1967.
11. A. B. P. LEVER, *Co-ord. Chem. Rev.*, 1968, 6, 119.